

Adopting and Adapting Mobile-Based Learning as an Innovative Trend in English Language Teaching

Mahak Habib

Department of English, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6542477>

Published Date: 12-May-2022

Abstract: The present study provides background on mobile learning and how it can be used to enhance the whole E-Learning system. It also highlights the advantages and future of mobile-based learning with respect to English language teaching. Mobile-based learning is a new model of learning, that provides a combined, informal, and student-centred learning environment. It is considered the ultimate type of learning and its unique capabilities have great potential to enhance teaching and learning experiences. It is an educational interaction between learners and the learning materials, which can be accessed from anywhere. Mobile-based learning also gives us the opportunity to modify the existing learning strategies in order to give learners a higher adjustable approach to handling their learning experiences. It has become a vital tool for the education system and can add to the overall learning experience of students and teachers.

Keywords: mobile-based learning, E-learning, environment, education system.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most attractive technologies in mobile technology represents a revolutionary approach to education. In recent times mobile devices have been steadily incorporated into learning. The broad use of Smartphones and different transportable and Wi-Fi gadgets has converted the traditional teaching method and learning process. Mobile-based learning is a powerful method for engaging learners on their own terms and enhances their broader learning experience because of its mobility quality and supporting platform.

The term mobile stands for mobility or the ability to move freely and easily from one place to another. Mobile-based learning refers to the implementation of mobile devices in any branch of study. The feature of mobile technology such as portability and information accessibility plays a major role in the enhancement of English language teaching and learning. To successfully adopt mobile-based learning, attention must be given to these

influential factors. Thus, the influential factors were classified into three main categories with several subcategories. The three main categories are the features of the devices, user's expectations and pedagogical advantage. Mobile technologies affected the way people interact with each other, and how people communicate and work. Traditional teaching and learning paradigms have been shaken by the impact of the integration of e-learning tools into educational practices.

II. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

M – Learning or the use of mobile technologies has been observed as an important element in the teaching-learning experiences. With the widespread of mobile technology, learning can occur at any time and any place even if teachers and students are not in the same physical or temporal location. Mobile technologies give a new paradigm in connectivity,

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences

Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (8-11), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

communication, and collaboration in our daily lives. When considering the value of mobile-based learning in education, it is relevant to consider what is good and beneficial for the learners. M-Learning is learning with a specific device, at any time and in any place. Moreover, most modern learners who oftentimes are forced to study anywhere and anytime have demanded applying portable technologies.

Mobile-based learning offers flexibility in when the learning takes place and teaches relevant skills for the future. It is the outcome of technologies enabled through appropriate use. Mobile learning is diverse from traditional electronic learning, thus the conventional pedagogical theory should be revised to fit the characteristics of the mobile environment. The enhanced pedagogical learning process is utilized to facilitate the learning in mobile learning activities. Methods of teaching and the teacher's views of learning are an essential part of the educational use of technology. Pedagogical theories and strategies are normally strongly linked to learning theories so the way to use mobile devices to support learning widely depends on the learning theory. I quote Herrington and Herrington who stated that "Adopting more recent theories of learning has the potential to exploit the affordances of the technologies in more valuable ways". Many researchers have explored the relationship between existing learning theories and mobile learning.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The significance of the present study can be summarized as follows:

1. To simplify language learning through the use of familiar technology.
2. To familiarize the LSRW skills.
3. To identify the effectiveness of teaching LSRW skills through mobile technology
4. To enable learning experience possible anywhere and anytime
5. To foster the use of the English language for communication.
6. To facilitate the learning process as students have the possibility to explore, analyze, discover, and choose activities which are real and meaningful.
7. To enhance interaction between real and virtual environments.
8. To promote self-learning and learning by doing & fun.
9. To create a learner-centered approach.

IV. MOBILE-BASED ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING

There are different types of activities emphasizing vocabulary learning through mobile phones, depending on the level of language proficiency of the students. We have different activities for enhancing the vocabulary of the learners. With the advancement of the new generation of mobile phones, it is now possible to design a mobile system for learning listening skills through listening exercises. On the other hand, Grammatical points can be learnt through a specifically designed program installed on mobile devices, in which grammatical rules are taught, followed by multiple-choice activities where students select the correct answer from the given alternatives. Grammatical exercises can be in the form of 'true-false' or 'fill-in the blanks' which are to be responded to by the learners. They can also learn the correct pronunciation of unfamiliar or new words to be able to fulfill their learning needs. Mobile devices with multimedia functions give the learners the opportunity to record their own voices. Reading activities can be offered to learners either via a well-designed learning course installed on mobile devices. When the learners are able to articulate the correct pronunciation of a word then he/she will be able to speak correctly. There are certain English learning tools for improving the writing skills of the students. Mobile devices have some applications for detecting errors in their writing. So, in this way, we can enhance our LSRW skills through mobile-assisted English language learning and teaching.

Mobile-based learning offers many benefits to reach the learners in various ways and to improve the education they are receiving. Traditionally, students used to sit in the classroom for six hours and the teachers expect students to learn. But

International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social SciencesVol. 9, Issue 3, pp: (8-11), Month: May - June 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

nowadays learning can occur anywhere, anytime with a technological device. It also provides a medium that enhances higher-order thinking skills. There are many advantages that mobile-based learning can enhance traditional classroom setup and improve pedagogy such as:

1. Support distance learning
2. Can enhance student-centered learning.
3. It can be used more effectively for the differently-abled.
4. Can enhance interaction between and among students, learners and instructors.
5. Providing a learning experience outside the classroom.
6. Making the learning experience enjoyable by recording, and organizing over time
7. Efface the fear of language learning
8. Promote self-learning of the learners.
9. Comfortable, handy, portable and compatible for learning.
10. Learning can be possible anywhere and anytime.
11. Use of mobile devices to support the practice of achieving listening and speaking skills effectively
12. The usefulness of the mobile technology used for vocabulary acquisition
13. Focusing on grammar learning, pronunciation and writing skills.

On the other hand, there are some barriers to mobile-based learning including:

1. Small screen size so eyes are vexed faster.
2. Limited memory size.
3. Small and uncomfortable keyboards.
4. Battery drains out faster when we use the internet.
5. Smartphone costs us the most.
6. Fear of misplacement, oblivion, stolen or corruption.
7. Difficulty to use mobile devices in noisy environments.
8. Poor network connectivity.

V. CONCLUSION

Mobile technologies induce the impact of mobile learning on traditional pedagogical learning strategies. The mobile-based learning model emphasized mobile users, learning strategies, situated environments, and virtual group awareness. With the enhanced pedagogical learning strategies, learners acquire skills and knowledge in a situated classroom. Mobile technology does not aim to perplex the learning process but facilitates mobile learners' learning process. To create new innovative learning opportunities, one needs to take into account usability and rationality. We believe that the suitable application of mobile devices is to be developed in the combination of the appropriate use of mobile technology and enhanced educational ground.

M-Learning empowers students to enhance their literacy skills and recognize their abilities. It can be used to enhance both self-learning and collaborative learning experiences. M-Learning promotes learners to work upon their hard spots and improve the areas where they lag behind. Hence, the integration of mobile-based learning with English teaching and learning may offer vast innovations in the coming days.

REFERENCES

- [1] Herrington and J. Herrington. (2007). Authentic mobile learning in higher education. In AARE2007 International Educational Research Conference.
- [2] Behera, S. K. (2013). E- and M-learning: A comparative study. *International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications*, 4(3), 65 – 78. Retrieved from <http://www.ijonte.org/FileUpload/ks63207/File/08.behera.pdf>
- [3] Evans, C. (2008). The effectiveness of m-learning in the form of podcast revision lectures in higher education. *Computers & Education*, 50(2), 491-498.
- [4] Kuznekoff, J. & Titsworth, S. (2013). The impact of mobile phone usage on student learning. *Communication Education*, 62(3), 223-252.
- [5] Mahmood, M. D., Raheem, B. R., & Nehal, R. (2022). Developing multiple intelligences through different learning styles: An integrated approach to learner-centered pedagogy. *Journal La Edusci*, 3(1), 13-17.
- [6] Raheem, B. R., & Khan, M. A. (2020). The role of e-learning in COVID-19 crisis. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 8(3), 3135-3138.
- [7] Raheem, B., Mahmood, M. D., Taher, G. A., & Shakeel, Z. (2022). A study on the use of smartphone applications in English language learning with special reference to covid-19 pandemic. *Journal La Edusci*, 3(2), 37-46.
- [8] Raheem, B.R., & Khan, M. (2020). The significant use of ICT tools in English language teaching and learning with special reference to the covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering and Management*, 5(10).251-256
- [9] Swan, K., A. Kratcoski, et al. (2007). Highly mobile devices, pedagogical possibilities, and how teaching needs to be conceptualized to realize them. *Educational technology magazine: The magazine for managers of change in education* 47(3). 10 -12.